

Optical characteristics of urban waters containing humic substances

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The Murinsky creek is a tributary of the river Okhta, which is the most polluted river in Saint-Petersburg. Water samples of the Murinsky creek were studied to suggest optical parameters for location of wastewater outlets, polluting the urban flow. The following indicators (variables) of water were measured: concentrations of main ions, electric conductivity (EC), optical density at 254 nm (D_{254}), fluorescence intensity in UV region at certain excitation and emission wavelengths ($I_{ex,em}$), total organic carbon (TOC), inorganic carbon (IC), total nitrogen (TN).

Principal component analysis found 6 significant principal components (PC). Three of them formed 87% of data dispersion. According to the loadings PC1 could be responsible for wastewater pollution. PC 1 explains 44% of data dispersion. Variables have high and moderate positive loadings (0.64...0.87) on PC1 for main ions concentrations, EC and TN, and also protein-like fluorescence (emission at 300-350 nm). This is typical for pollution with municipal wastewater. D_{254} has negative loading on PC1 (-0.64), TOC and humic-like fluorescence (emission at 420 nm) has insignificant negative loadings (-0.02...-0.22). This can be explained by high natural background formed by humic substances in unpolluted creek water, which does not allow wastewater to increase TOC and humic-like fluorescence after mixing with natural water.

PC2 has negative loadings (-0.14...-0.50) for EC and main ions concentrations and positive loadings for TN, D_{254} , protein-like and humic-like fluorescence (0.13...0.69). PC2 could also be responsible for organic components of wastewater.

PC3 has positive loadings on EC, TOC, D_{254} , humic-like fluorescence (0.34...0.64), negative loading for TN and protein-like fluorescence (-0.08...-0.39). Maybe PC 3 is responsible for natural background variations, explained by humic substances.

These results of PC analysis have some common features with results for river Okhta [1]. Both investigations allow to suggest the most suitable combination of variables as indicators of water pollution: EC and $I_{230,350}$.

References

1. Chabina E.A., Andrianova M.Ju. Fluorometricheskij monitoring zagraznenij rechnoj vody // Bidiagnostica sostojanija prirodnykh i pripidno-technogennyh system: Materials of XXII All-Russian scientific and practical conference with international participation, Kirov, November 18–19, 2024. – Kirov: Vyatka state university, 2024. – pp. 32-36. – EDN FPWCSO.